

MANAGEMENT OF NIGERIAN SUPERFICIAL FUNGAL INFECTIONS.

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ABSTRACT

Ringworm infections which are mild communicable fungal infections are made up of *Tinea capitis* (ringworm of the scalp), *Tinea corporis* (ringworm of the glabrous skin), *Tinea cruris* (ringworm of the groin), *Tinea manuum* (ringworm of the hand), *Tinea pedis* (ringworm of the foot) and *Tinea unguim* (ringworm of the nail). It has been very difficult to manage these superficial fungal infections in Nigeria. This stems from impatience, poverty, inadequate levels of hygiene, and the emergence of fungal strains that are resistant to fungal disease drugs. In this study, commonly used fungicidal preparations were assessed for their effectiveness on locally isolated dermatophytes. These included Sodium dimethyl thiocarbonate, Griseofulvin, Haloprogin, Boric acid, Naphthiomate T, Clotrimazole, Cuprinol clear, a combination of Clotrimazole and Cuprinol clear among others. The test fungi included *Microsporum audouinii*, *M. canis*, *M. ferrugineum*, *M. gypseum*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum*, *T. schoenleinii*, *T. tonsurans*, *T. violaceum*, *T. megninii*, *T. yaoundei* and *Epidermophyton floccosum*. Discs of 1cm Whatman filter paper impregnated with the minimum inhibitory concentration of each of the preparations were used against each of the test fungi. The culture plates were incubated at 27°C for 5days and were observed for inhibitory effect. The fungicidal preparations showed strong inhibitory effects on the dermatophytes. Griseofulvin, Haloprogin, Phenyl acetate, Salicylic acid, and Naphthiomate T gave 100% inhibitory effects. Best result was obtained with a combination of Clotrimazole and Cuprinol Clear. Topical fungistatic agents as Clotrimazole and Cuprinol Clear could be administered as important therapeutic adjunct in the treatment of superficial infections.

KEYWORDS: Management, superficial fungal infections, griseofulvin, dermatophytes, Nigerian.

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INTRODUCTION

Many drugs and a few physical methods have been used in the management of human mycotic diseases. Descriptions of fungistatic or fungitoxic (an agent that inhibits but does not necessarily kill fungi) and fungicidal (an agent that kills fungi) preparations should contain names of those substances which by appropriate testing means, have been shown to possess antifungal properties per se and not merely curative influences on the human mycoses. The use of roentgen-ray epilation in the treatment of human *Tinea capitis* is an example of this reasoning. The therapeutic endeavour in this case, epilation, is concerned more with the elimination of the diseased part, a kind of radiation surgery than with the actual destruction of the pathogenic organisms. Similar conditions also hold for the so-called keratolytic agents, the best example being salicylic acid. They also perform an amputation of the diseased epidermis, chemical in this case, in the hope of eradicating the infection.

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Mechanical scrapping and sandpapering of nails in Onychomycosis are procedures of similar purpose, to partially eliminate the diseased area and also as auxiliary measures to render the infected portion of the skin more amenable to actual chemotherapy. Some agents such as powders inhibit the propagation of fungi by preventing skin maceration and hyperhidrosis by altering the ecological conditions. Other substances employed in the treatment of mycoses are mainly palliatives, allaying the symptoms of acute inflammation and irritation. Examples of these are potassium permanganate aluminum acetate and to a certain extent, boric acid.

These compounds may possess a slight fungistatic power, however, their main therapeutic purposes are those of soothing and a stringency. Therefore, it should not be assumed that an agent is either fungistatic or fungicidal simply because established usage places it in the medical armamentarium of mycotic therapy.

The mechanism of antifungal action is also not well understood. The main avenues of antifungal mechanism seem to be:

- (1) Oxidation
- (2) Reduction
- (3) Protein precipitation
- (4) Enzyme poisoning
- (5) Deprivation of trace metal action by chelating agents
- (6) Competitive inhibition
- (7) Osmotic changes

However, since knowledge of the efficiency of many compounds is gained only through empiricism and clinical observation, a classification of compounds from the point of view of their possible mechanism of action is almost impossible. This is true because many compounds tested *in vitro* and found active fungistatically or fungicidally were unsuitable for actual therapy, since they were primary irritants or potential skin sensitzers. As many of the established antifungal substances, such as sulphur, have been in use since antiquity, the newer ones used in clinical medicine have borrowed heavily from the experience and vast research material presented by the plant pathologist. Fatty acids, hydroxyquinoline, benzothiazole and quinines are but a few examples of this lend-lease programme (Oster and Woodside,1977).

In 1957, a relatively pessimistic view of the state of antifungal therapy was presented in Reddish's Antiseptics, Disinfectants, Fungicides and Sterilization. This picture has now changed drastically with the advent of the newer antimycotic antibiotics. Of the group of highly active polyenic antibiotics, only nystatin (Hazen and Brown, 1951) was discussed.

In 1956, Gold *et al.* reported the first *in vitro* activity of *Streptomyces nodosus* products which inhibited the growth of *Candida albicans*, among others. This discovery led to the isolation and purification of amphotericin B for the treatment systemic mycotic infections of man. Griseofulvin, now considered the most valuable antimycotic for superficial fungus infection was discovered by oxford and associated in 1939. Its antifungal properties in human mycosis, however remained unrecognized until 1958. Griseofulvin is the first systematically absorbed antimycotic which exerts positive action on superficial fungus infections, including those affecting the hair and nails. One of the recent additions to the drugs used in the treatment of systemic mycoses is 5-fluorocytosine.

Various antimycotic agents for the management of superficial fungal infections are currently available in the Nigerian drug market. Some of these drugs are effective but some are adulterated while some are completely rubbish. In order to make sure that Nigerians receive the values of their money when they purchase such drugs, a survey was therefore carried out to determine the effectiveness of such commonly used skin disease drugs on superficial fungal infections.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Commonly used fungicidal preparations in Nigeria were tested for their effectiveness on locally isolated dermatophytes. The fungicidal preparations included Sodium dimethyl thiocarbonate, Griseofulvin, Haloprogin, Boric acid, Phenyl nitrate, Phenyl acetate, Salicylic acid, Arylthionocarbamate, Naphthiomate T, Clotrimazole, Cuprinol clear and a combination of Clotrimazole and Cuprinol clear. The minimal inhibitory concentrations of the various fungicides were determined and used to impregnate sterile discs of 1cm Whatman filter paper respectively. Three of such impregnated discs were planted around a new culture of each of the test fungi (dermatophytes). The resultant culture plates were incubated at 27°C and observed for the impregnated discs inhibitory effects. Ten culture plates were employed for each test fungus. The test fungi included *Microsporum audouinii*, *M. canis*, *M. ferrugineum*, *M. gypseum*, *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *T. rubrum*, *T. schoenleinii*, *T. tonsurans*, *T. violaceum*, *T. megninii*, *T. yaoundei* and *Epidermophyton floccosum*. Control plates were also set up but in this case they contained only the test dermatophytes and sterile non-fungicide impregnated discs of Whatman filter paper. Scorings on the inhibitory effects of the Superficial fungal disease drugs on the dermatophytes were made appropriately.

RESULTS

The fungicidal preparations showed strong inhibitory effects on the dermatophytes. The best result was obtained with a combination of Clotrimazole and Cuprinol Clear. Good results were also obtained from Clotrimazole and Cuprinol clear when they were used singly. Griseofulvin, Haloprogin, Phenyl acetate, Salicylic acid, and Naphthiomate T gave 100% inhibitory effects. Sodium dimethyl thiocarbonate also produced inhibitory effect good result although its action was not tested on *M. ferrugineum*. The details of the results are given in Table 1. The summary of the results is presented in Figures 1 and 2.

Table 1: The effect of some fungicidal preparations on species of fungi associated with superficial fungal infections in Nigeria

Fungicidal preparations	Effects on dermatophytes												Total
	Ma ^o	Me	Mf	Mg	Tm	Tr	Ts	Tt	Tv	Tg	Ty	Ef	
Sodium dimethyl thiocarbonate	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	11
Griseofulvin	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Haloprogin	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Boric acid	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-	10
Phenyl nitrate	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Phenyl acetate	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Salicylic acid	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Aryl thionocarbonate	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	7
Naphthiomate T	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Clotrimazole	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Cuprinol Clear	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12
Clotrimazole plus Cuprinol Clear	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	12*
Total	11	11	10	11	12	12	12	12	12	11	12	10	136

Ma (*Microsporum audouinii*) Me (*M. canis*) Mf (*M. ferrugineum*) Mg (*M. gypseum*)

Tm (*Trichophyton mentagrophytes*) Tr (*T. rubrum*) Ts (*T. schoenleinii*) Tt (*T. tonsurans*)

Tv (*T. violaceum*) Tg (*T. megninii*) Ty (*T. yaoundei*) Ef *Epidermophyton floccosum*

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Figure 1: No of dermatophytes affected by each of the fungicidal preparation with standard error

Figure 2: Total no of fungicides having effect on each dermatophyte with standard error.

Ma (*Microsporum audouinii*), Me (*M. canis*), Mf (*M. ferrugineum*), Mg (*M. gypseum*), Tm (*Trichophyton mentagraphytes*), Tr (*T. rubrum*), Ts (*T. schoenleinii*), Tt (*T. tonsurans*), Tv (*T. violaceum*), Tg (*T. megninii*), Ty (*T. yaoundei*), Ef (*Epidermophyton floccosum*)

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DISCUSSION

The fungicidal preparations were found to inhibit the growth of the test dermatophytes. Griseofulvin was found to have 100% inhibition. Chemically, griseofulvin is 7-chloro-2' 4, 6-trimethoxy-6'-methylspiro [benzofuran -2 (3H), 1'- [2]-cyclohexene]-3,4'-dione. It is a colourless, odourless, neutral compound that is slightly soluble in water (approximately 10mcg per ml). The dry powder is thermostable. The fungicide was first isolated in 1939 as a metabolic product of *Penicillium griseofulvum*. Later investigators observed a stunting and curling effect of the hyphae of *Botrytis allii* by a metabolite of a *Penicillium* species (Brian *et al.* 1946). This was termed the "curling factor" and was subsequently identified as griseofulvin. Oster and Woodside (1977) reported that oral griseofulvin has been used successfully in recent years against superficial infections caused by *Microsporum*, *Trichophyton* and *Epidermophyton* species. The same authors reported that the absorption of griseofulvin from the gastrointestinal tract is satisfactory and that the antibiotic reaches the infected and cornified structures in a biologically active form. McNall (1960) and El-Nakeeb and associates (1965) demonstrated that griseofulvin inhibits nucleic acid synthesis of the inhibited dermatophytes.

Haloprogin was also found to be very effective against the test fungal species. Haloprogin is a synthetic fungal topical agent which is used as a 1% solution or cream for the treatment of superficial fungal infections of the skin. Chemically, the compound is 3-iodo-2-propynyl-2,5 trichlorophenyl ether. The drug is used for topical treatment of tinea pedis, tinea cruris and tinea corporis caused by *T. rubrum*, *T. tonsurans*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis*, *E. floccosum* and *Malassezia furfur*. It has been reported that 15% of the compound in a cream application is recovered from urine within 5 days. There is little information on the range and severity of the adverse effects.

Both Phenyl nitrate and Phenyl acetate were found to be inhibitory on the test fungi. The two fungicides have been widely used in the treatment of various cases of dermatophytosis. Salicylic acid showed 100% inhibitory effect on the test dermatophytes. This fungicide together with benzoic acid is one of the oldest and most commonly used remedies against derma tophytosis. It is known as Whitfield's ointment when it is combined with benzoic acid in a proportion of 6% Salicylic acid and 12% benzoic acid.

Naphthiomate T was found to have 100% inhibitory effect on the test fungi. This preparation is more generally known by its generic name, tolnaftate. A 1% solution in a polyethylene glycol vehicle, is used topically for the treatment of superficial fungal infections caused by *T. rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. gypseum*, *E. floccosum*, *Malassezia furfur*. Tolnaftate is employed as an auxiliary to griseofulvin in the treatment of thickens lesions of the palms and soles.

Clotrimazole and Cuprinol Clear had total inhibitory effects on the test fungi. Clotrimazole is presently being used for topical therapy on superficial mycoses. The compound is applied as a 1% cream or solution. It has been used successfully in the treatment of tinea versicolor and candidiasis. This preparation which is sold as Clotrimazole 1% is a broad-spectrum fungicidal, antimycotic agent and has the trade name Mycoten® Cream. It is sold in packs of 20g. One gram of the cream contains 10mg bis-phenyl- (2-chlorophenyl)-l-imidazolyl-methane.

Cuprinol Clear has very strong fungicidal action on dermatophytes. Dilutions of it can be obtained with the aid of white spirit A combination of Clotrimazole and Cuprinol Clear produced excellent inhibitory effects on the test dermatophytes. In the choice of topical preparations for the management of superficial fungal infections, attempts should be made in selecting antimycotic agents that do not induce skin irritation, sensitization and skin staining. Attempts should also be made in using constituents that are not carcinogenic to the skin. As the skin texture is restored, percentages of bacterial antibiotics should be introduced into the antimycotic preparation as adjuncts for the control of bacterial population. This will help restore the normal skin microflora. However, antibiotics abuse should be avoided.

Effort should be made not to use any of the fake or adulterated antimycotic creams in the market as this might complicate the successful management of the superficial fungal infections Nigeria.

Superficial fungal disease patients should be patient and adhere to the doctors prescriptions as such would go a long way in making them receive a quick and permanent cure of the fungal infections. Fungal disease patients should be kept out of humid and dusty environments. Fungal disease patients should avoid the sharing of their towels and articles of clothing with healthy individuals. Such practice would reduce the spread of the fungal diseases. People should stop sharing their residential houses with domestic animals for fear of such animals being stolen. Superficial fungal disease patients should be subjected to diets that contain fruits and vegetables. Such diets will help ward off such superficial fungal diseases. This is because these super foods contain immune-boosting antioxidants. The antioxidants are vitamins, minerals and other nutrients that protect and prevent the cells from damages caused by free radicals. Free radicals can interfere with the immune system. The three major antioxidant vitamins are beta-carotene, vitamin C and Vitamin E.

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REFERENCES

- Brain, P.W., Curtis, P. J. and Hemming, H. J. (1946). Biologic assay, Production and isolation of "curling factor". *Trans. Br. Mycol. Soc.* **29**:173.
- El-Nakeeb, M.A. and Lampen, J.O. (1965). Uptake of griseofulvin by the sensitive dermatophytes, *Microsporum gypseum*. *J. Bacteriol*, **89**:564.
- El-Nakeeb, M.A., McLellan, W.L. and Lampen, J.O. (1965). Antibiotic action of griseofulvin and dermatophytes. *J. Bacteriol* **89**:557.
- Gold, W., Stout, H.A., Pagano, J.S. and Donovan, R. (1956). Amphotericins A and B: antifungal antibiotics produced by a streptomycete I. In vitro studies In: *Antibiotics Annual 1955-1956*. p. 579. Medical Encyclopedia, Inc. New York.
- Hazen, E.L. and Brown, R. (1951). Fungicidin, an antibiotic produced by a soil actinomycete. *Proc. Soc. Exp. Bio. Med.*, **76**:93.
- McNall, E.G. (1960). Biochemical studies on the metabolism of griseofulvin. *Arch. Dermatol.* **81**:657.
- Oster, K.A. and Woodside, B.S. (1977). Fungistatic and Fungicidal Compounds. In: *Disinfection, Sterilization and Preservation*. (Seymour S. Block, ed.) p. 442-461. Publ. Henry Kimpton Publishers, London.

